

CRACoWi
Cybersecurity Compliance Made Easy

Threat Modelling under the Cyber Resilience Act

CRAcademy

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WHAT IS IT?

Threat Modelling is a process to identify the possible threats to a device or solution. The goal is to find weaknesses before attackers can take advantage of them. This is a fundamental element of the Cyber Resilience Act, and proactively undertaking this process is an important step in security-by-design.

There are many ways to do threat modelling, you should pick the one that works best for your use case. In our case, we followed the following steps:

System Context

Map the scope at three levels using Data Flow Diagrams

STRIDE

Identify threats systematically

Mitre ATT&CK / EMB3D

Refine threats with real-world attack techniques

1. Map the System Context using DPD diagrams. Begin with Level 0 and continue to the appropriate level depending on your device/solution.
 - Level 0 - Device is a black box. Identify entry points and other components in the environment.
 - Level 1 - Document edge services and internal components, determine trust zones and boundaries.
 - Level 2 - Document services and their versions, logic, storage and physical interfaces.
2. Map the STRIDE threats at each level.
3. Map the STRIDE threats to Mitre EMB3D or ATT&CK.
4. Risk Assessment - evaluate and prioritize threats.
5. Mitigate or accept risk.
6. Update and review on a regular basis or when changes occur.

USEFUL LINKS

- Draw.io - Tool for creating diagrams, DFDs, etc.
<https://www.drawio.com/>
- Data Flow Diagrams - Tool to visually show device/solution
<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/software-engineering/levels-in-data-flow-diagrams-dfd/>
- STRIDE - Threat Modelling framework
https://owasp.org/www-community/Threat_Modeling_Process#stride
- Bunkai platform - IoT security testing platform
<https://bunkai.io>
- One Key platform - Firmware analysis, SBOM platform
<https://onekey.com>
- Mitre ATT&CK - Knowledge base of adversarial tactics
<https://attack.mitre.org/>
- Mitre EMB3D - Knowledge base of adversarial tactics for IoT
<https://emb3d.mitre.org/>
- CVSS Calculator - Tool to determine severity and impact of threats
<https://chandanbn.github.io/cvss/>
- Threat Dragon - OWASP Threat Modelling tool
<https://www.threatdragon.com>

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